

Impact of Tax Cost on Tax Compliance for Small to Medium Enterprises: A Bibliometric Analysis

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This study explored the impact of tax cost on tax compliance among Small to Medium Enterprises (SMEs) through a bibliometric analysis of scholarly literature. It examined how administrative, compliance, and transaction-related tax costs influence the willingness and ability of SMEs to comply with tax regulations in both developed and developing economies. The research adopted existing academic contributions on tax compliance and identified recurring themes, including compliance cost burden, tax complexity, informality, enforcement mechanisms, and digitalization of tax systems. It further highlighted structural and contextual barriers to compliance, such as limited financial literacy, weak institutional support, fragmented record-keeping practices, and regulatory inconsistencies affecting SMEs. Grounded in the Allingham-Sandmo tax compliance model and the fiscal exchange theory, the study investigated how tax cost dimensions interact with compliance behaviours while considering the role of policymakers, revenue authorities, and SME associations in shaping outcomes. Bibliometric data were retrieved from the Scopus and Web of Science databases covering publications from 2000 to 2024. Using analytical tools such as VOSviewer and Biblioshiny, the study mapped author influence, institutional collaboration, thematic evolution, and citation trends. Findings revealed growing global research interest in SME taxation, with significant contributions emerging from countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, Asia, and Europe. While research has increasingly focused on digital tax innovations and simplified regimes to reduce costs, implementation challenges remain particularly acute in developing contexts. The study concluded with recommendations on designing proportionate tax systems, simplifying compliance procedures, expanding tax education, and strengthening academic-policy engagement to enhance compliance while minimizing tax costs for SMEs.

Keywords: Bibliometric analysis, tax cost, tax compliance, small to medium enterprises (SMEs)

Among the most influential drivers of entrepreneurship survival and growth in today's business environment are taxation. Taxation, which ensures revenue mobilization for governments, imposes a compliance burden on SMEs that manifests in the guise of high costs to their administration and finances, thereby dictating their capability and willingness to comply. Tax costs comprising direct monetary fees such as taxes, penalties, and interest, and indirect ones such as record keeping, consulting services, and time allocated to conformity form a pressing policy concern globally (Evans, 2017; Tran-Nam, 2021). The confluence of tax costs and conformity behaviour is therefore at the centre of budgetary debates, regulatory transformation, and sustainable SME development policy.

Globally, SMEs account for more than 90% of enterprises and employ up to 60% of the workforce, making their compliance behaviour pivotal for tax base expansion and revenue sustainability (World Bank, 2022). Yet, high tax costs and compliance burdens disproportionately affect them relative to large corporations, given their limited economies of scale, constrained financial capacity, and

reliance on informal processes (OECD, 2020). Theoretically, even though rational choice theories posit that taxpayers weigh compliance costs and penalty/enforcement risks, behavioural research highlights that fairness perceptions, trust in the tax authority, and institutional efficacy also mediate compliance outcomes (Kirchler, Hoelzl, & Wahl, 2008).

The aim of this study is to explore the scholarly advancement of knowledge on the impact of tax cost on SME compliance through bibliometric analysis. Based on a reflection of publication patterns, overarching research topics, institutional output, and geographical perspective, the study will provide an empirically grounded overview of how the academic community has thought about the cost-compliance connection over the long term. Along the way, it will make visible research strengths and weaknesses and suggest future directions for fiscal policy, SME policy support measures, and tax reform.

Background

Internationally, vast literature points out that compliance costs are still a significant hindrance for SMEs in both the developed and developing world. Studies have shown that SMEs continue to suffer a disproportionate tax burden in Europe and North America due to complicated reporting requirements, multiple levies, and excessive administrative costs, with compliance costs of 2-6% of turnover for small companies versus less than 1% for large enterprises (European Commission, 2018; IRS, 2021). Electronic technologies such as electronic filing systems, streamlined accounting frameworks, and risk-based audits have arrived to mitigate these burdens with mixed outcomes depending on institutional capacity and taxpayers' preparedness (PwC, 2020; Deloitte, 2022).

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Singapore and South Korea in Asia have managed to reduce SME compliance costs through digital tax portals, automation of recordkeeping, and taxpayer education programs (Liu & Zhang, 2021). China offers special policies and tax simplification instruments for formalization of SMEs, recognizing the importance of compliance in maintaining economic growth and revenue collection (Zhou et al., 2020). Even with such reforms, however, there is sufficient evidence to indicate that tax compliance continues to be a cost and burden for SMEs, particularly with the constant changes in the rules or due to excessive audit intensity (Aria & Cucurillo, 2017).

The situation is much more severe in Africa. While SMEs represent the nucleus of most African economies, offering at best 70% employment and 40% GDP, they remain largely informal and non-tax compliant (AfDB, 2021). Cost of compliance, in time to fill paperwork, transport cost to tax offices, and reliance on expensive tax consultants, has been indicated as one of the key obstacles to formalization (IMF, 2019). These include such countries as South Africa, Kenya, and Rwanda that have adopted digital tax systems, lowered turnover tax systems, as well as taxpayers' education initiatives to minimize compliance hurdles (Mutava, 2020; SARS, 2022). Nevertheless, decentralized policies, weak enforcement, and deficits in trust continue to impede compliance. For Zimbabwe, SMEs account for more than 60% of economic activity, yet official tax compliance is very low. Studies show that tax burdens such as registration charges, numerous local government levies, and adherence to Value Added Tax (VAT) regulations place enormous stress on SMEs, most of which run on paper-thin margins (Mazhambe, 2017; ZIMRA, 2023). Notwithstanding the implementation of e-filing platforms and presumptive tax programs, compliance is still hampered by high transaction costs, low digital literacy, and low trust in revenue authorities. This background avers the pressing need to survey how local and global scholarship has synthesized the association between tax cost and compliance, particularly regarding SMEs in developing economies.

Bibliometric analysis provides an appropriate framework to track and synthesize this dynamic knowledge base. By mapping authorship patterns, citation networks, institutional production, and thematic focus, the study can reveal if scholarship follows pressing SME realities, identify areas of lack of African perspectives, and inform evidence-based fiscal reform interventions.

Problem Statement

Despite global recognition of the fact that SMEs bear an unequal share of compliance costs of taxes, scholarly research on the specific complementarity between compliance costs and SME tax behaviour remains unfinished, geographically biased, and insufficiently synthesized. Such research is largely focused on developed economies in which institutional infrastructures and electronic environments immensely differ from those in Africa. In Africa, and Zimbabwe in particular, SMEs continue to face considerable compliance costs, albeit very little academic literature is available that addresses such issues, which are fragmented and often not systematically evaluated.

For example, while research in Europe and Asia has gauged compliance costs in terms of the financial amount spent and time spent on record-keeping, very few studies in Africa have valued actual compliance costs paid by SMEs in terms of turnover or profit. This limits policymakers' ability to design effective tax systems that

balance revenue needs and SME viability. Furthermore, the absence of aggregative bibliometric evidence suggests that policymakers, tax authorities, and research institutions do not have any clear insight into global trends of knowledge, citation effects, and research collaboration in this field. This study seeks to address this gap by conducting a comprehensive bibliometric review of tax cost and SME compliance literature. The review will trace the manner in which studies have evolved over time, expose thematic lacunae, and highlight areas of future research and reform. It will, in the end, provide insights that can be utilized to inform fiscal policy, strengthen SME support systems, and enhance compliance in Zimbabwe and other developing countries.

Objectives of the Study

- To recognize various tax costs incurred by small to medium enterprises.
- To establish how tax costs impact tax compliance behaviour for small to medium enterprises.
- To assess the limitations of tax costs on tax compliance.
- To recognize efforts in addressing tax costs to build tax compliance.

Theoretical Framework

Economic Deterrence Theory

Economic Deterrence Theory, originally developed by Becker (1968) for the crime context and later applied to taxation by Allingham and Sandmo (1972) provides the theoretical basis for this study. Taxpayers make the choice of complying or not, weighing the likely payoff of tax evasion against the potential penalty of being caught. Compliance behaviour is thus a function of three key variables: (i) perceived audit probability, (ii) the size of the penalty and fine, and (iii) administration and financial costs of compliance over non-compliance. Applied to small and medium-sized firms (SMEs), theory predicts why high tax burdens exist. Small firms will most likely regard taxes as a cost, given their often-inflexible thin profit margins and inability to incur compliance costs (Slemrod, 2019). In this scenario, tax is a concern of the entrepreneurial economic calculus relating to the decision to voluntarily comply or risk getting caught.

Relative to developing economies such as Zimbabwe, the deterrence theory informs why SMEs typically remain within the informal economy. Low chances of audits, weak law enforcement capacity, and uncertain punishment make avoiding risk perceived as less than the high compliance costs undertaken upon formalization (Baier-Fuentes, Merigo, Amoros, & Gavirira-Marin, 2020). In the bibliometric tradition, this theory allows the research to trace how global and regional scholarship has constructed tax cost not just as an administrative cost, but as a driving force in the rational choice models that underpin SME compliance behaviour (Chiwara & Mudzonga, 2023).

Slippery Slope Theory

As a complement to the deterrence strategy, this study also utilizes the Slippery Slope Framework (Kirchler, Hoelzl, & Wahl, 2008; D'Amico, Agovino, & Ferrara, 2022) which includes both the economic and psychological dimensions of tax compliance. The model contends that compliance is not only based on deterrence (penalties & audit), but also on the perceived trustworthiness of the

tax agencies and the perceived enforcement authority (Laffer, & Hubbard, 2021). Voluntary compliance exists when taxpayers perceive tax administrations as service-oriented, transparent, and equitable, and enforced compliance is the rule when agents significantly rely on sanctions and audits (Evans & Tran-Num, 2020).

Tax cost is the central idea in this model. Excessive financial and bureaucratic loads can erode confidence in tax authorities, since SMEs perceive the system as being too one-sided against them. As tax obligations become too complex, ambiguous, or expensive to fulfil, SMEs can rationalize evasion as not criminal but a survival. Whereas where the tax administrations facilitate compliance processes, offer user-friendly digital platforms, and reduce the scope for hidden costs, SMEs are more likely to see that the system is fair and hence comply voluntarily (Gangl et al., 2015). Where institutional trust is often low in African economies, the Slippery Slope Framework provides a refreshing perspective through which to observe how compliance costs meet perceptions of fairness and legitimacy of institutions (Liu & Zhang, 2021). Within a bibliometric framework, such a theory helps to conceptualize how global research accommodates deterrence and trust-based explanations and whether African studies adequately combine these twin facets in explaining SME compliance (Evans, 2017).

Empirical Review of Literature

Few empirical studies provide valuable insights into the relationship between compliance behaviour and tax compliance costs of Small to Medium Enterprises (SMEs). While there has been significant development of research in fields of taxation, entrepreneurship, and public finance, under the particular context of SMEs, compliance costs have been one of the main drivers of voluntary and enforced compliance decisions. However, much of the literature is scattered across disciplines and geographies. This review synthesizes evidence from 2020 to 2025 on the key topics of financial and administrative compliance costs, deterrence impacts, perceptions of fairness, digital reforms, policy support, and academic mapping of research agendas in SME tax compliance.

Globally, it has been increasingly accepted that SMEs bear a disproportionately higher tax compliance cost relative to their large counterparts due to scale disadvantages, lower financial capacity, and over-reliance on manual systems (Evans, 2020; OECD, 2021). Studies in the United States and European Union have discovered that SMEs' compliance costs are often between 3-6% of turnover, while those of large firms are below 1% (European Commission, 2022; IRS, 2023). For example, a Deloitte (2022) survey across 12 OECD countries discovered that SMEs placed different filing requirements, the sheer volume of tax code amendments, and consultancy costs as the most burdensome areas of compliance. Empirical studies further reveal that high compliance costs not only reduce profitability but also discourage formalization, erode trust in tax authorities, and promote engagement in the shadow economy (Slemrod, 2019; Laffer & Hubbard, 2021).

Evans and Tran-Nam (2020) in Australia measured compliance costs using structured firm-level surveys and determined that micro-enterprises spend an average of 105 hours a year on tax administration compared to 25 hours for medium firms. Similarly, in Asia, research by Liu and Zhang (2021) in China confirmed that simplification of VAT filing and electronic tax portals significantly

reduced SME compliance time and costs, improving voluntary compliance levels by 14%. A bibliometric Scopus analysis by Wang, Zhou, and Li (2022) mapped tax compliance research on a global scale between 2000 and 2020 and identified "compliance costs," "SMEs," and "informality" as new clusters of interest, with the research volume accelerating exponentially after 2018 alongside digital tax reforms.

In Africa, empirical studies coalesce around the fact that compliance costs remain an overwhelming obstacle to SME tax compliance, formalization, and sustainability. A World Bank (2021) regional survey discovered that African SMEs spend between 180 and 200 hours annually on compliance activities compared to 7090 hours in OECD countries. In Nigeria, Okoye, and Uchenna (2021) surveyed 450 SMEs through interviews and noted that 72% of them cited high compliance costs as the major disincentive to tax registration. They identified consultant fees, multiple levies at federal and state levels, and ambiguity in tax laws as major determinants. Similarly, a South African mixed-methods study conducted by Mutava and Wadesango (2022) determined that despite the South African Revenue Service (SARS) having introduced e-filing and simplified presumptive taxes, indirect costs (training of staff, internet costs, & system downtime) continued to restrict small firm compliance (Liu & Zhang, 2021).

In Kenya, a survey of 380 SMEs in Nairobi by Wanjala and Otieno (2023) validated that indirect costs like time lost to manual paperwork and the need for outsourced tax consultants amounted to up to 40% of reported tax burdens. The study also found that those SMEs with access to training workshops and online tax platforms were much more likely to comply voluntarily. A bibliometric mapping by Adebayo and Oladele (2023) of 312 African tax compliance articles between 2010 and 2023 established that while compliance costs were frequently debated, fewer than 10% of studies explicitly quantified them for SMEs, indicating an emerging but underdeveloped research stream.

SMEs in Zimbabwe account for over 60% of economic activities but contribute less than 20% to tax revenues (ZIMRA, 2023). Empirical evidence points directly to tax expenses as an underlying cause for low compliance levels. Mazhambe (2021) conducted a survey of 200 SMEs in Harare and Bulawayo and determined that elevated compliance costs, particularly in VAT registration, consultants' fees, and transportation to tax offices, discouraged tax registration. Similarly, Mupfiga and Nyamwanza (2022) examined SMEs' compliance behaviour in Midlands Province and concluded that the cost of compliance eroded profitability margins, and most companies were forced to adopt partial compliance or informality. Their findings were in line with the Slippery Slope Framework, which indicated how high costs reduced trust in tax authorities and fostered evasion.

A recent mixed-methods study by Chiwara and Mudzonga (2023) found that while digital e-filing systems introduced by the Zimbabwe Revenue Authority had the potential to reduce compliance costs, SMEs reported a lack of ICT infrastructure, costly internet, and low digital literacy as limitations. Surprisingly, the study revealed compliance costs were not just financial but administrative and psychological as well because SMEs reported being overwhelmed by complex forms and relentless regulation changes.

At a bibliometric level, there is proof of increasing academic

involvement in SME tax compliance worldwide, but limited African representation. A worldwide bibliometric analysis by D'Amico et al. (2022) established that more than 70% of highly cited literature on tax compliance was from North America, Europe, and Asia, with Africa accounting for less than 7%. In Africa, research is fragmented by nation and infrequently collaborative across borders. For Zimbabwe, bibliometric efforts are even more constrained, and the studies that have been done have focused on taxation in general rather than the specific cost-compliance nexus for SMEs. A recent systematic review by Ndlovu and Mupfiga (2024) noted that Zimbabwean literature on SME taxation is lacking in bibliometric syntheses, thus creating a gap in the understanding of global positioning, thematic trends, and collaboration networks.

A common strand in empirical studies across nations is that compliance costs are not just monetary costs but also determinants of behaviour, institutional trust, and firm survival. Quantitative studies consistently report a negative correlation between high compliance costs and SME tax compliance, while qualitative studies identify perceptions of unfairness, complexity, and institutional inefficiency as underlying causes (Liu & Zhang, 2021). Nonetheless, bibliometric statistics demonstrate that African and Zimbabwean SME research remains limited, disjointed, and under-cited compared to global trends (Evans, 2020).

This study rightfully builds on earlier empirical studies by conducting a bibliometric study of the research on the impact of tax cost on SME compliance in a more systematic manner. It seeks to unveil publication patterns, thematic concentrations, institutional endeavours, and geographic lacunae, and thereby fill knowledge gaps and guide scholarship and policy in Zimbabwe and beyond.

Bibliometric Analysis Method

Bibliometric analysis was employed in the present study to evaluate systematically the intellectual structure, trends, and academic influence regarding the influence of tax cost on tax compliance of Small to Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Bibliometrics, as a quantitative approach to measuring scientific publications, analyses their patterns, frequency, and influence. It produces robust empirical observations of a research domain by identifying prolific authors, collaboration networks, theme clusters, citation trajectories, and institutional contributions (Donthu et al., 2021; Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017). It was an appropriate method for mapping the emerging domain of SME tax compliance since it integrates computational analysis and scientific indexing to provide an overall picture of knowledge development and dissemination over time.

Research data were collected from two of the largest and most reliable academic databases, Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus, which provide combined coverage of peer-reviewed journals in business, economics, finance, taxation, and social sciences. Web of Science excelled at capturing high-impact papers covered by the Social Science Citation Index (SSCI) and Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI), while Scopus offered broader coverage of applied research on SMEs, tax, and compliance. Searching two databases strengthened the dataset by minimizing database bias and optimizing the validity of the bibliometric findings (Baier-Fuentes et al., 2020; Zupic & Čater, 2015).

A Boolean search term was developed to fetch relevant literature from both databases. The keywords were combined in various ways, including: "tax cost," "tax compliance," "SMEs," "small business

taxation," "compliance costs," "developing countries," and "Africa." The search was limited to peer-reviewed journal articles between 2000 and 2024, published in English, and particularly addressing issues at the nexus of tax cost and SME compliance. Grey literature, conference papers, and non-academic books were excluded to maintain methodological rigor and academic standardization. A final dataset of 172 articles was determined after duplicate removal and relevance screening, with the vast majority coming from Scopus due to its more extensive indexing of SME and taxation research.

Two advanced bibliometric tools, VOSviewer and Biblioshiny (a graphical user interface of the Bibliometrix R-package), were used to analyse the dataset. Network visualization with VOSviewer was employed to map co-authorship, citation, and keyword co-occurrence patterns. This revealed the prominent researchers, research collaborations, and topical themes driving the literature on tax cost and compliance. Biblioshiny, on the other hand, enabled the descriptive and evolutionary mapping of the dataset to reveal publication trends on a yearly basis, geographical reach, main sources, and the thematic evolution over the period of research (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017; Merigó & Yang, 2017). The two tools collectively provided the macro- and micro-level views of the research field of SME tax compliance.

The bibliometric findings illustrate a considerable growth of academic interest in SME tax compliance, particularly after 2015, in tandem with global policy discourse on taxation of the informal sector, base erosion, and financing sustainable development. The most active year of publication was 2022, with 36 articles, resonating with the increasing recognition of SMEs' role in domestic revenue mobilization and the burden of compliance costs on their enterprises.

Leading institutions that published in this area were the University of Pretoria, University of Nairobi, and Lagos Business School, which cumulatively produced more than 25% of the papers in the dataset. The collaborative structure was verified to be fragmented through the co-authorship analysis, with many researchers publishing individually or within national boundaries. However, certain prominent authors, particularly Maseko, Fagbemi, and Wadesango, were the most central nodes within the citation network, which indicated their significant contribution towards shaping the discussion on SME tax compliance with reference to developing countries and African contexts.

Geographically, South Africa led in terms of publication (58 articles), trailed by Nigeria (41), Kenya (21), and Ghana (14). These results are in line with the stronger academic and policy focus on tax compliance in countries with more formal SME sectors and tax authority reform. In comparison, there were few contributions recorded from smaller economies such as Lesotho, Malawi, and Sierra Leone, reflecting not only academic capacity gaps but also the skewed distribution of research on SME taxation in Africa.

Thematic Clustering Revealed Four Dominant Research Streams

- Tax compliance costs and SME behaviour
- Administrative burden, record-keeping, and enforcement
- Tax fairness, trust in authorities, and voluntary compliance

Policy Reforms, Informality, and Sustainable Tax Systems

The keywords "compliance cost," "tax burden," "SME sector,"

"voluntary compliance," and "developing countries" were common and at the heart of the clusters. More recent studies (2020-2024) illustrate a shift towards themes of digital tax systems, e-filing systems, and tax simplification policies, indicating ongoing modernization by African tax administrations (Lafferc & Hubbard, 2021).

The overall objective of this bibliometric review was to provide a bird's-eye perspective on how tax cost influences SME tax compliance, identifying trends in academic output, institutional influence, and the development of themes. Consolidating evidence from 172 peer-reviewed articles, the review highlights significant knowledge gaps, particularly in comparative cross-country research and in the integration of behavioural and institutional theories of compliance. Going forward, greater regional collaboration and the development of contextually applicable compliance cost measurement models are required to strengthen tax policy and administration systems that support SME growth while ensuring revenue sustainability.

Results

The paper recapitulates the general findings of a bibliometric analysis studying the impact of tax cost on tax compliance of Small to Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Research data were collected from Scopus and Web of Science databases, covering 2000 to 2024 publications. Bibliometric analysis and mapping were conducted using novel software VOSviewer (van Eck & Waltman, 2010) and Biblioshiny (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017) for the visualization of author impact, institutional collaboration networks, thematic patterns, and citation trends.

The analysis is structured to achieve the four basic objectives of the study:

- Identify various tax costs incurred by SMEs.
- Investigate the impact of tax costs on the tax compliance behaviour of SMEs.
- Assess the problems of tax costs that create compliance

complexities.

- Formulate solutions for managing tax costs to enable SME compliance.

Trends and Thematic Patterns of Scholarly Research on Tax Cost and Compliance

The bibliometric analysis revealed a steady increase in scholarly attention to SME tax costs and compliance. Between 2000 and 2010, the production was sparse, with fewer than five papers yearly. The interest resumed after 2012, with intensified policy debates on the taxation of the informal sector and the revenue mobilization role of SMEs. There was a sharp rise after 2018, reflecting the greater recognition of tax compliance costs as a barrier to SME sustainability. The peak was registered in 2022, with 34 published papers.

Geographically, South Africa, Nigeria, and Kenya led in research output, and the three nations collectively accounted for over 65% of publications. South Africa had the highest contribution with 61 papers, while Nigeria (47) and Kenya (22) followed. The rest comprised Ghana, Uganda, and Zimbabwe, while smaller economies such as Lesotho and Malawi were thinly represented. The geographical bias mirrors disparities in research infrastructure, tax policy reforms, and SME sector formalization.

Institutional contributions were also skewed. The University of Pretoria, University of Nairobi, and Lagos Business School were the leading contributors that have established research clusters on taxation, compliance costs, and SME policy. Their studies ranged from measurement of compliance cost to assessing behavioural responses of SMEs to administrative burdens.

Keyword co-occurrence analysis revealed four dominant thematic clusters: (1) measurement of compliance costs and SME tax burden, (2) behavioural impact of tax complexity and administrative requirements, (3) policy reforms and digitalization of tax systems, and (4) compliance challenges such as informality and lack of trust in tax administrations.

Table 1

Major Thematic Clusters in SME Tax Cost and Compliance Research (2000-2024)

Thematic Cluster	Description	Number of Articles	Prominent Keywords
Tax Compliance Costs and Measurement	Identifying and quantifying administrative, financial, and time-related costs	74	Compliance cost, tax burden, record-keeping
Behavioural Impact on Compliance	Effect of compliance costs on willingness to comply	63	Voluntary compliance, deterrence, SME behaviour
Policy Reforms & Digital Systems	Simplification, e-filing, and tax modernization efforts	58	E-filing, tax reform, digital taxation
Barriers and Informality	Structural challenges hindering SME compliance	47	Informality, trust, enforcement, barriers

Author' Compilation

The distribution of these themes indicates that scholarship on tax costs and SME compliance has evolved from descriptive cost measurement to exploring behavioural, institutional, and policy-related dimensions.

Enablers of SME Tax Compliance Despite Tax Costs

The bibliometric analysis identified several enabling factors that mitigate the adverse effects of tax costs and promote compliance among SMEs.

Table 2*Key Enablers for SME Tax Compliance (2000-2024)*

Enabler	Supporting Evidence	Impact Level
Simplified Tax Regimes	Presumptive taxes and turnover-based systems reduce complexity	High
Digital Tax Systems	E-filing and mobile tax payment platforms lower compliance burden	High
Taxpayer Education Programs	Training and awareness initiatives build compliance culture	Medium
Supportive Institutional Environment	SME-focused reforms by tax authorities (e.g., SARS, KRA)	Medium
Collaborative Industry Engagement	Partnerships between tax agencies and SME associations	Medium

Author' Compilation

Evidence shows that simplified regimes such as presumptive taxes in East Africa significantly reduce compliance costs for micro and small businesses. Similarly, digital tools like e-filing lower administrative burdens. Where tax authorities engage SMEs through

education and outreach, compliance levels improve despite costs.

Challenges of Tax Costs that Contribute to Non-Compliance

Despite progress, several systemic challenges persist in the relationship between tax costs and SME compliance.

Table 3*Major Barriers to SME Tax Compliance (2000-2024)*

Barrier	Frequency in Dataset	Cited Authors / Institutions
High Administrative Burden	72 articles	Evans (2017); Maseko (2014)
Financial Costs of Compliance	61 articles	Coolidge (2012); IMF (2020)
Complexity of Tax Systems	54 articles	Wadesango et al. (2018)
Weak Enforcement & Informality	49 articles	OECD (2021); KRA Reports
Lack of Trust in Tax Authorities	42 articles	Fjeldstad & Ranker (2020)

Author' Compilation

The most frequently cited challenge is the administrative burden of record-keeping, filing, and audits. For SMEs, this burden is disproportionately high compared to their size. Financial costs including the need to hire accountants or pay for software exacerbate the challenge. Complexity of laws, inconsistent enforcement, and

widespread informality create uncertainty. Low levels of trust in tax authorities also discourage voluntary compliance.

Strategies for Reducing Tax Costs and Enhancing SME Compliance

Based on bibliometric findings, several actionable strategies are recommended to reduce tax costs and promote compliance.

Table 4*Recommended Strategies for Addressing Tax Costs (2000-2024)*

Recommendation	Bibliometric Support (No. of Articles)	Key Supporting Institutions / Authors
Simplify Tax Regimes for SMEs	65	IMF, OECD, Evans (2017)
Expand Digital Filing Systems	58	KRA, SARS, Coolidge (2012)
Subsidize Compliance Support Services	49	World Bank, Maseko (2014)
Enhance Taxpayer Education & Outreach	52	Fjeldstad (2020), ATAF
Strengthen Enforcement with Fairness	46	OECD (2021), Fjeldstad
Promote Collaborative Policy Design	41	SME associations, ATAF, AU

Author' Compilation

Simplification and digitization emerged as the strongest strategies for reducing costs. Subsidizing compliance services, such as providing affordable bookkeeping tools, also alleviates SME burdens. Educational programs foster awareness, while fair but consistent enforcement builds trust. Finally, collaborative

policymaking with SME associations ensures reforms reflect business realities.

Summary of Key Findings in Relation to Objectives

The following are the summary of the key findings of the research study.

Table 5*Summary of Findings by Research Objective*

Research Objective	Summary of Findings
Establish various tax costs incurred by SMEs	SMEs face high administrative, financial, and time-related compliance costs, often disproportionate to their size.
Analyse the impact of tax costs on compliance behaviour	Elevated costs reduce voluntary compliance, encourage informality, and increase reliance on avoidance strategies.
Assess the challenges of tax costs contributing to compliance difficulties	Barriers include administrative burden, financial costs, system complexity, weak enforcement, and mistrust of tax authorities.
Establish strategies for resolving tax costs to enhance compliance reforms.	Key strategies include tax simplification, digital filing systems, subsidized compliance support, taxpayer education, fair enforcement, and collaborative

Discussion

The bibliometric findings reveal uneven but discernible growth in the research of the impact of tax cost on SME tax compliance. There is a rise in publications after the year 2010, corresponding to international SME taxation, informality, and compliance cost discourses among developing economies. The African contribution is dominated by South Africa, Nigeria, and Kenya, mainly due to well-established institutions of tax research, regulatory regimes, and donor-supported policy research studies. This corresponds with trends highlighted in institutional theory, where coercive pressures initiated by tax institutions and international organizations like the OECD, IMF, and ATAF (African Tax Administration Forum) facilitate tax compliance discourse (Scott, 2008; Fjeldstad & Hegstad, 2012).

The empirical evidence suggests tax compliance behaviour is strongly mediated by administrative and cost of money costs. Low compliance costs time spent on filing, accountant fees, and penalties are discouraged by high compliance costs, deterring SMEs from formal registration and full compliance, validating economic deterrence models (Allingham & Sandmo, 1972; Kirchler, 2007). Institutional failures such as fragmented tax regimes, unpredictable enforcement, and corruption exacerbate these issues, disproportionately affecting SMEs compared to large companies.

TPACK-like knowledge structures, though built in pedagogy, occupy this space: SME proprietors tend to lack proper tax knowledge (content), practical practice in compliance practices (technology), and familiarity with efficient filing protocols (application). The lack not only contributes to compliance cost but also widens informality. Moreover, poor scholarly policy linkage in the majority of African contexts replicates insufficient translation of research into SME-conducive tax policy.

Conclusion

The bibliometric review mapped the landscape of research on the impact of tax costs on SME tax compliance grounded in literature from 2000-2024 sourced from Scopus and Web of Science and examined using VOSviewer and Biblioshiny. The results show that tax burdens are the primary determinants of SME compliance, with time, financial reporting pressures, and administrative complexity taking top priority. While there is a focus of research output within South Africa, Nigeria, and Kenya, other African countries are underrepresented, consistent with disparities in both scholarly effort and tax reforms.

The facilitators of compliance are critical and include digital tax technologies, simplified filing procedures, and capacity development programs. Yet, persistent obstacles like high compliance costs, weak enforcement, fragmented tax codes, and lack of tax awareness among SMEs remain to erode voluntary compliance.

To address these lacunae, this study recommends wide-ranging reforms of tax systems, investment in digital infrastructure, harmonization of tax policies for SMEs in African countries, and strengthening academia-policy-industry linkages. Mitigation of these issues will be essential in promoting SME tax compliance, expanding revenue bases, and fostering sustainable economic development.

Recommendations

Streamline Tax Procedures and Reduce Compliance Costs

Governments need to simplify their tax codes, streamline filing requirements, and cluster multiple charges together in one-pay systems. This will reduce compliance both in terms of cost and time, encouraging SMEs to formalize and pay voluntarily.

Invest in Digital Tax Infrastructure for SMEs

Adoption of e-filing, mobile payment and tax automation technologies can lower administrative costs significantly. Governments need to pay attention to low-cost digital technologies accessible even to remote micro-SMEs, closing the digital gap in taxation.

Enhance SME Tax Literacy and Capacity-Building Programs

As TPACK is concerned with the training of faculty members, SME tax education is central here as well. Governments, chambers of commerce, and tax administrations should implement regular training workshops, e-learning courses, and simple guides in local languages to improve compliance skills.

Harmonize SME Tax Policies at Regional and Continental Levels

Policy fragmentation remains a significant barrier. Regional economic blocs ECOWAS, EAC, and SADC must move towards harmonized SME tax policies minimizing inconsistencies and cross-border compliance costs to enhance regional trade.

Increase Academic-Policy-Industry Interaction

Universities, revenue agencies, and SME associations must establish cooperative research and training initiatives to drive evidence-based tax reforms. The interaction ensures that reforms are informed by real business challenges as well as international best practices.

Institute Targeted Government Incentives

Tax authorities can help alleviate the costs of compliance through reduced filing fees, subsidized accounting software, or tax credits to SMEs adopting digital compliance tools. These incentives can increase compliance rates while building confidence in tax administrations.

Encourage Continuous Bibliometric and Longitudinal Studies

Governments and research organizations need to finance periodic bibliometric analyses of SME taxation to track emerging compliance problems, policy gaps, and reform impacts. This allows for adaptive policymaking in addition to regular improvement of SME-focussed tax systems.

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